

INFLUENCE OF 3D WEAVING PARAMETERS ON PREFORM COMPRESSION AND LAMINATE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

3D woven composites have emerged as a new class of material with applications in various sectors such as aerospace, military, maritime, infrastructure and wind energy. Despite many advantages, there are concerns about the degradation of in-plane mechanical properties of the 3D woven composites mainly due to the tow waviness. Yarn tensions during the weaving process have a significant influence on the crimp in the 3D woven preforms. In the present work 3D weave architectures are manufactured by changing weave parameters such as tow tension and the binder density. Effect of binder density on the compressibility of the dry 3D woven preforms is studied. The mechanical properties of the woven composites made with various binder densities and tow tension variations are evaluated. Tow geometry parameters are measured by using microscopy and X-ray CT.

1 INTRODUCTION

There has been a growing interest in 3D weaving in particular as a means of reducing manufacturing costs and improving through-thickness properties. The ability to arrange fibres in different orientations is the biggest advantages of the 3D woven composites. Weave topology plays a significant role in determining the mechanical properties and failure mechanisms of 3D woven composites [1]. However, z tow interlacement points increase the stress concentration and affect the mechanical properties of composites [2]. The through-thickness z tow interlacements also have an impact on the in-plane fibre volume fraction and the respective planar properties [3, 4].

It was found that the through-thickness interlacements and the thickness of 3D woven reinforcements reduce the formability compared to 2D fabrics. However, the compressibility of the reinforcement is highly relevant as it influences the fibre volume fraction in the reinforcements [5-7]. Different researchers have studied the compressional and tensile properties of textile preforms [8-10]. Tow geometry of fabrics has also been investigated [11].

This research systematically investigates the influence of binder density and stuffer tensions for different weave architectures namely orthogonal, angle interlock and layer-to-layer, on the preform and laminate mechanical properties. Areal density (g/m^2) of all the samples has been kept constant while varying other parameters. To our knowledge, most of the literature on 3D woven composites is based on commercial fabrics with limited control on process parameters.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials

Mechanical properties of the textile composites mainly depend on the fibre orientation and the binding pattern, especially in 3D woven composites. Three types of 3D weave architectures were manufactured in the present work. Through-the-thickness orthogonal weave (ORT): In the ORT weave structure, warp binders were used and the binder goes through all the layers of weft tows as shows in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Orthogonal through-the-thickness weave architecture; (a) side view of the weave showing binding pattern (b) top view of the weave.

Through-the-thickness angle interlock weave (AI): the interlacements of all the layers were carried out by using binders. The binder interlaced through-the-thickness of the fabric in the angular path as shown in Figure 2. The weave structure is less compact than the ORT weave architecture.

Figure 2: Angle interlock through-the-thickness weave architecture; (a) side view of the weave showing binding pattern (b) top view of the weave.

Layer-to-layer weave (LTL): The weave architecture with the layer to layer interlacements was manufactured. Binder interlaced two adjacent weft layers of the fabric as shown in the side view of the fabric in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Layer-to-layer weave architecture; (a) side view of the weave showing binding pattern (b) top view of the weave.

3D woven fabrics were manufactured by changing two parameters: (a) tow densities, and (b) tow tensions. Commonly stuffers are used for the interlacement in angle interlock and layer-to-layer weaves structures. However, in this research work, all the weave structures were manufactured by using warp binders for the interlacements. The stuffers were designed to stay straight in the weave geometry in all three weave structures.

To keep the areal weight of the fabrics constant, weft densities were changed as per the change in binder densities. Tenax-E HTS45 E23 12K carbon fibre was used as a warp and weft stuffers and Tenax-E HTA40 E13 6K carbon fibre was used as binders for this study. Table 1 shows the weave structures manufactured with various binder densities.

Fabric type	Tow density (tows/cm)			Layers		Areal Weight (gsm)	Thickness (mm)
	Warp	Weft	Binder	Warp	Weft		
AI6.25	10.52	13.68	0.675	4	5	1995 ± 18	3.63 ± 0.15
AI12.5	10.52	13.27	1.35	4	5	2018 ± 23	3.33 ± 0.14
AI25	10.52	12.44	2.7	4	5	1972 ± 21	3.06 ± 0.12
LTL6.25	10.52	13.68	0.675	4	5	2006 ± 20	3.63 ± 0.14
LTL12.5	10.52	13.27	1.35	4	5	1986 ± 26	3.46 ± 0.14
LTL25	10.52	12.44	2.7	4	5	1959 ± 14	3.36 ± 0.13
ORT6.25	10.52	13.68	0.675	4	5	2014 ± 21	3.33 ± 0.12
ORT12.5	10.52	13.27	1.35	4	5	2014 ± 19	3.26 ± 0.10
ORT25	10.52	12.44	2.7	4	5	1979 ± 14	2.73 ± 0.09

Table 1: Weave specifications of 3D woven fabrics made with variations in binder density.

Glass fibre tow (PPG Hybon 2002 1200 tex) too, was used as a weft tow to study the effect of weft tensioning on the fabric architecture. Weave specifications of the orthogonal woven fabrics with the tow tension variations are shown in Table 2.

Fabric type	Tow density (tows/cm)			Layers		Areal Weight (gsm)	Thickness (mm)	Tow tensions (cN)	
	Warp	Weft	Binder	Warp	Weft			Warp	Weft
ORT W1	10.52	13.27	1.35	4	5	2525 (± 21)	3.46 (± 0.14)	112	66
ORT W2	10.52	13.27	1.35	4	5	2539 (± 25)	3.33 (± 0.11)	300	66
ORT F1	10.52	13.27	1.35	4	5	2532 (± 23)	2.73 (± 0.08)	79	45
ORT F2	10.52	13.27	1.35	4	5	2540 (± 21)	3.06 (± 0.10)	79	66
ORT F3	10.52	13.27	1.35	4	5	2529 (± 19)	3.36 (± 0.09)	79	91
ORT F4	10.52	13.27	1.35	4	5	2527 (± 23)	3.26 (± 0.09)	79	132

Table 2: Weave specifications of the fabric manufactured with tow tension variations.

2.2 Transverse compression

Transverse compression tests on 3D fabrics made with tow density variations were carried out by using Instron 5569 universal testing machine as shown in Figure 4. The 3D woven fabric samples were cut into 10 cm X 10 cm pieces. Quasi-static compression tests were carried out, where, the compression testing machine was run continuously at a constant speed of 1 mm/min and the pressure thickness curve was recorded.

Figure 4: Instron testing set up for transverse compression

2.3 Tensile testing

A bi-functional epoxy resin (Araldite LY 564) along with the hardener (Aradur 2954) supplied by Huntsman was used for manufacturing the composite laminates. The pressure of ~1 bar was applied during vacuum bagging infusion process. Specimens for the tensile tests were prepared by cutting all the laminates in the warp direction. The tensile test procedure was followed as per the ASTM standard D3039. A specimen size of 250 mm X 25 mm was used for the samples with tow density variations. The Instron 5982 R2680 testing machine and a video extensometer were used to perform the test. A minimum of four specimens were tested for the fabrics with tow density variations and a minimum of three specimens were tested for the fabrics with tension variations.

2.4 Optical microscopy

Samples were prepared in different three orthogonal planes to study warp, weft and binder tow paths. Keyence VHX-5000 Optical microscope was used to study the internal geometry of 3D woven preforms at the 200 X.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Compression study

The thickness results of different 3D fabric structures with the pressure up to a range of 1000 kPa are demonstrated in Figure 5. It is clearly evident that the thickness of all the structures decreased with increase in pressure and the behavior of the curves is same as predicted by the pressure thickness curve in the literature. The highest reduction in thickness over the increase in pressure was observed in pressure range up to 100 kPa, being representative of vacuum infusion process. Comparatively less reduction in the thickness was observed after 100 kPa.

Figure 5 : Pressure thickness curve of fabric structures with lowest (a), mid (b) and highest (c) binder density.

In all these three types of fabrics, the least thickness reduction was observed in ORT weave structure which may be attributed to the interlacement pattern of binder yarn. The binders were interlacing the weft layers in through the thickness direction with a pattern of 1/1 giving stability to fabric layers by avoiding their shifting. While in AI and LTL, the fabric layers could shift relative to each other which allow the layers to nest with each other, consequently reducing the thickness of the 3D structures.

The effect of binder density on compaction behaviour of individual structures was also studied and the pressure thickness response of all the three structures with varying binder densities is presented in Figure 6. It can be seen that for AI structure, the thickness reduction increased with increasing binder density. The highest thickness reduction was observed in highest binder density weave structures while least thickness was recorded when binder density was lowest in all three cases. With LTL structure, again highest thickness reduction was observed in LTL25. The least thickness reduction was exhibited in LTL12.5 instead of LTL 6.25 as observed in the previous case of AI weave structures. The effect of binder density on ORT structure presented the same trend as AI structure with highest thickness reduction with highest binder density and least thickness reduction with least binder density.

Figure 6: Pressure thickness curve of AI (a), LTL (b) and ORT (c) structure with varying binder densities.

Overall the trend of thickness reduction with the binder density in all three structures followed the same pattern with highest thickness reduction observed in structures with highest binder density. However, different behavior in the results was observed in LTL structures, where the least thickness reduction was observed in the case of LTL6.25. It could be considered that the low compactness of the LTL 6.25 structure compared to the other LTL structures caused this behavior. Further investigation by using X-Ray CT images can be carried out to study this phenomenon. The highest thickness reduction in 3D fabrics with increasing binder density can be attributed to the reason that presence of binders in the 3D structure creates gaps among warp and weft layers allowing more spreading of the tows on compaction due to available gaps with adjacent tows. Additionally more gaps in the tows will allow the tows in the adjacent layers to nest with each other resulting higher thickness reduction of the preform.

3.2 In-plane tension properties

In-plane tension tests were carried out in the warp direction for all the weave structures. The elastic modulus of the composites was measured within a strain range of 0.1%-0.3%. Values of the tensile strength and tensile modulus were normalised for the meaningful comparison as the composites were varied in the volume fractions.

Following equation (1) was used to calculate the normalised strength and normalised modulus.

$$\sigma_{nor(vf)} = \sigma(FVF_{av}/FVF) \text{-----(1)}$$

Where,

$\sigma_{nor(vf)}$ = Normalised stress;

σ = Ultimate tensile strength;

FVF_{av} = Average fibre volume fraction of composites with tow density variation;
 FVF = Fibre volume fraction of the structure.

Fibre volume fraction of the composites with the tow tension variations was calculated theoretically by using the areal weight of the fabrics.

Figure 7 Tensile modulus (a) and strength (b) of the weave structures with binder density variations.

The tensile strength and modulus data of the weave structures with different binder densities is given in Figure 7. Angle interlock and layer-to-layer weave structures with high binding density exhibited higher strength; however, in the orthogonal structure the strength was less. The tensile strength of the ORT 6.25 shows the highest strength among the orthogonal weave structures. The ORT 6.25 weave structure had the lowest crimp compared to ORT 25 and ORT12.5. The Tow bundle effect due to the lesser binder density has led to the less crimp and higher tensile strength. ORT 25 weave structure has the highest crimp in the warp stuffers which have affected the tensile strength of the composite.

All the weave structures were made with the same weave parameters except tow density and binder interlacement pattern; hence the binder density of the fabric influenced the tensile properties of the composites.

In angle interlock and the layer-to-layer weave structures, binders also contribute under the loading condition since the binder crimp is usually significantly low compared to orthogonal weave structures, resulting in higher strength in AI25 and LTL25. Although LTL25 had slight less crimp in warp stuffers compared to AI25, AI25 demonstrated little higher tensile strength. The reason might be the interlacement pattern of the weave structure. In the layer-to-layer weave structure, the binding interlacements are in between two adjacent weft layers. This interlacement pattern causes a less integrated and less compacted weave structure. Similar effects of the binders can be seen in the weave structures made with the mid binder density. In addition tensile modulus also exhibited the similar behavior.

Figure 8 Tensile modulus (a) and strength (b) data of the orthogonal weave structures with tow tension variations

The weave structures with the warp tension variations showed prominent changes in the stress-strain curve as shown in Figure 8. ORT W1 with less warp tension exhibited higher strain compared to ORT W2 weave structure, which was manufactured with the higher warp stuffer tension.

A gradual reduction in the strength of the tested samples upon an increase in the weft tows tension was observed. In addition, ORT F1 exhibited highest stiffness values in the warp direction followed by ORT F2, ORT F3 and ORT F4 weave structures. The primary reason is due the increasing crimp in the load bearing warp tows. Increase tension on the weft tow during weaving process led to the higher tow waviness on the warp stuffers. The tensile strength values of the composites made with warp tow tension variations showed the influence of the tow tension parameter on the composites. ORT W2 exhibited higher tensile strength in the comparison with ORT W1 due to the reduction in the load bearing warp tow waviness.

Weave structures made with warp tension variations showed an increase in the modulus with the higher tow tension. ORT W1 weave structure showed lower modulus compared to ORT W2. It was observed that ORT F2, ORT F3 and ORT F4 exhibited very similar modulus values after normalisation.

3.4 Microscopic analysis of tow geometry and X-ray CT

Tow dimensions and crimp percentages of all three tows (warp, weft and binder) were measured for all the fabrics made with binder density and tow tension variations in Figure 9 and Figure 10.

Figure 9 Cross section image of binder path in ORT 25 (a), AI 25 (b) & LTL 25 (c) weave structure

Figure 10 CT image of Orthogonal weave

Amongst all three 3D weave structures, the layer-to-layer weave structure appeared very differently in the cross sectional images of the composite. The binders in the LTL weave structure, interlaced with two layers of the weft stuffers. Due to the layer to layer interlacement, the weave structure is less compacted. Simultaneously, due to the change in the tow arrangements it was only possible to get one binder and two stuffers in one cross section plane. The measurement of tow geometries was misleading in the layer-to-layer woven fabric because of the tow bundle formation due to the less interlacements. Unawareness of overlapping pattern of two or four tows may lead to the wrong assumption of the tow dimensions. Hence for the layer-to-layer woven preforms, tow dimensions were not measured from the cross section images.

Orthogonal through-the-thickness 3D woven composites made with different weft and warp tensions were also analysed. It was observed from the tow dimension measurements that the change in tension during weaving process has less effect on the tow width as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 Tow width (a) and thickness (b) measurement in the 3D woven composite made with different binder density

It was observed that warp tow width increases and weft tow width decreases with increasing the binder density. However, there is opposite effects on the tow thickness of the warp and weft tows. In the case of angle interlock weave structures weft thickness is not reducing significantly with increasing binder density.

Figure 12 Tow width (a) and thickness (b) measurement in the 3D woven composite made with different tow tension

In the case of composites made with different tow tension, there is no any significant difference in tow widths among the structures Figure 12 . Reduction in the weft tow thickness was observed in the ORT W2 (high warp tow tension) compared to ORT W1 (less warp tow tension). However, increasing trend was observed in the weft thickness with increasing weft tow tension except ORT F3.

Figure 13 % Crimp measurements of the composite made with binder density (a) and tow tension variation (b)

Measured values of the tow waviness in warp and weft stuffers in the composites with tow density variations are shown in Figure 13. Orthogonal weave structures have shown the high impact of binder density variation on the warp tow waviness. The standard deviation in the weft tow shows very high crimp in the top and bottom weft layers compared to the middle weft layers. Layer-to-layer weave structures showed less warp crimp compared to other weave structures. Angle interlock weave structures demonstrated the lowest weft tow waviness compared to the other weaves. Tow waviness in the binders was also measured in all the fabric type and LTL weave structures showed the lowest crimp in the binders due to its interlacement pattern.

It has been observed that the warp tows exhibited less crimp for the lowest weft tension weave structure. ORT F1 weave structure was manufactured with the lowest weft tension of 45 cN. Effect of warp tow tension can be clearly seen in the ORT W1 and ORT W2 weave structures. Higher warp tow waviness in ORT W1 and reduction in the crimp in ORT W2 represents the influence of tow tensioning on the internal geometry of 3D woven composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

- From the compressibility study, it was observed that the thickness reduction of the preform was higher with increasing binder density in the weave structures. The reason of this effect is due to the introduction of more binders the fabric becomes less compact giving rise to higher compressibility due to nesting of tows in the adjacent layers.
- The tensile test results showed that the tensile strength of AI and LTL increased with increase in binder density, whereas opposite trend was observed in the case of ORT structure. The reason of this was that in case of AI and LTL the binder also contributed towards the tensile strength. In case of ORT the binder density did not affect the tensile strength because of the binder orientation. It was also observed from the microscopic images that the binder of ORT structure exhibited highest waviness resulting least effect on tensile strength.
- In case of tow tension variations the tensile strength increased by increasing warp tensions due to decrease in tow waviness. While the tensile strength decreased by increasing weft tow tensions this was attributed to the reduction of warp tow crimp as studied by microscopic images. Geometrical analysis showed increase in warp tow waviness on increasing the weft tensions.

Detailed geometrical analysis of these 3D woven fabric samples by using X-ray CT to capture internal tow geometry, resin channels and their influence on resin flow will be presented in the future work.

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